

INVENTORY OF INCENTIVES APPLIED IN SOME EU COUNTRIES IN TERMS OF SOIL HEALTH PRACTICES FOR THE PERIOD 2014-2022

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Extended abstract

Incentives, in general, represent a complex and multifaceted concept with different understandings depending on the context and application. Incentives are often defined as any factor that motivates or encourages an individual or group to take a particular action (Ariely, 2016). According to this definition, incentives can take different forms, including monetary rewards, recognition, penalties, and social status. **The aim of the study is to present methodology and short results of the inventory incentives of several EU countries.** The analysis is part of wider research focused on the relation between the incentives, business models and ecosystem services (Nikolov et al, 2023).

Incentives related to soil health exist in various forms and can be implemented through different types of mechanisms. They can range from regulatory to voluntary, including public programs and private initiatives. Additionally, they encompass regulated offsets and emissions trading, direct Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES), certification, marketing labels, and adherence to cultural norms. These mechanisms can provide disincentives, such as use prohibition, fines, and taxes, as well as positive incentives, such as training, direct payment for land set aside, and improved market access. By combining these incentives, ecosystem service outcomes can be enhanced at lower social costs.

Garrett and Neves (2016) have identified different sources of short- and long-term incentive mechanisms and provided examples of their implementation (Figure 1). Their framework was used as a backbone of a constructed incentive typology.

The methodology and data collection includes the following aspects. To conduct the necessary analysis, a survey questionnaire was prepared for evaluating and describing incentives. The questionnaire is divided into two parts (Nikolov et al., 2023). The first part (Q1-Q6) consists of general questions about the surveying organization and country, identification of the incentive, land use classification, and NUTS level. The second part (Q7-Q15) collects information on whether the incentive is policy-driven or voluntary, the national policies supporting the application of such incentives, and the policies providing financial support for the incentive. It also explores the connection between the case study incentives and the main goals of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development objectives, as well as the key objectives of the new CAP 2023-2027. The final part focuses on gathering information about ecosystem services and their relationship with the incentives.

Empirical results show different aspects on both a national and an international level. Based on the collected information from our partners regarding incentives in different countries, we can classify them into three groups (Table 1). The results reveal variations among the countries, leading to their categorization into distinct groups according to the number of incentives.

Source: Garrett, L. and Neves, B. (2016) /

Figure 1. Incentives, investments, and mechanisms

The first group comprises countries with fewer than 10 incentives. These include Bulgaria, Denmark, Estonia, Latvia, and Spain. Among these countries, Denmark, Spain, and Latvia have the highest number of incentives, with 10 each. It is worth noting that Bulgaria, Latvia, and Estonia have a relatively balanced distribution between policy-driven and voluntary incentives, whereas Spain exclusively relies on policy-driven incentives.

The second group consists of Germany, England, France, and Italy, with a range of 16 to 30 incentives. Germany possesses the highest number of incentives within this group, with 30 in total. France and Italy also have a significant number of incentives, with 22 and 16 respectively. In this group, voluntary incentives dominate over policy-driven incentives, except for France, which does not have any policy-driven incentives.

The third group consists of the Netherlands, which stands alone with 76 incentives. The Netherlands exhibits a significantly higher number of incentives compared to the other countries. The focus in the Netherlands is primarily on policy-driven incentives, with 70 out of the 76 falling into this category. Only six incentives are voluntary in nature.

Table 1. Number of incentives by country

Country	Total	Policy-driven incentives	Voluntary incentives
Netherlands	76	70	6
Germany	30	4	26
England	31	4	27
France	22	0	22
Italy	16	4	12
Bulgaria	10	5	5
Denmark	10	7	3
Latvia	10	7	3
Spain	10	10	0
Estonia	8	6	2
Total	223	117	106

Source: Own calculations

The distribution of incentives varies among the countries. The Netherlands stands out with a high number of predominantly policy-driven incentives. In contrast, countries like Germany, England, France, and Italy have a considerable number of voluntary incentives. The rest of the countries in the dataset have a smaller number of incentives, and their distribution is relatively balanced between policy-driven and voluntary approaches.

Several conclusions are derived based on the information collected. In agricultural ecosystems, incentives influence ecosystem services through motivating changes in land use and management. This chain of influence is complex because incentives can cause multiple intended and unintended changes in land use and management, each potentially having co-benefits and trade-offs across multiple ecosystem services. In this research, there are identified and assessed incentives that can help the business model to become sustainable from the point of view of soil health. That goal is accomplished by exploring the incentives that drive farmers to act towards improving soil health.

It was collected and analysed 223 incentives in 10 countries participating in the NOVASOIL project. The countries were classified into three groups according to the number of incentives. The first group includes Bulgaria, Denmark, Estonia, Latvia, and Spain with a range from 8 to 10 incentives. The second group consist of Germany, England, France, and Italy, with a range from 16 to 30 incentives. The third group consists only of Netherlands, with 76 incentives. The Netherlands stands out with a high number of predominantly policy-driven incentives. In contrast, countries like Germany, England, France, and Italy have a considerable number of voluntary incentives. The other countries in the dataset have a smaller number of incentives, and their distribution is relatively balanced between policy-driven and voluntary approaches.

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